

Versioned Archive and Review of Biotic
Interactions and Taxon Names Found within
globalbioticinteractions/barnes
hash://md5/c971a5e01da53ef0227eee7a8c1d9ce7

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Abstract

Life on Earth is sustained by complex interactions between organisms and their environment. These biotic interactions can be captured in datasets and published digitally. We present a review and archiving process for such an openly accessible digital interactions dataset of known origin and discuss its outcome. The dataset under review, named globalbioticinteractions/barnes, has fingerprint hash://md5/c971a5e01da53ef0227eee7a8c1d9ce7, is 22.6MiB in size and contains 34,931 interactions with 1 unique type of association (e.g., eats) between 93 primary taxa (e.g., *Thunnus alalunga*) and 191 associated taxa (e.g., fish unidentified). This report includes detailed summaries of interaction data, a taxonomic review from multiple catalogs, and an archived version of the dataset from which the reviews are derived.

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Introduction

Data Review and Archive

Data review and archiving can be a time-consuming process, especially when done manually. This review report aims to help facilitate both activities. It automates the archiving of datasets, including Darwin Core archives, and is a citable backup of a version of the dataset. Additionally, an automatic review of species interaction claims made in the dataset is generated and registered with Global Biotic Interactions (J. H. Poelen, Simons, and Mungall 2014).

This review includes summary statistics about, and observations about, the dataset under review :

Barnes, C. et al., 2008. Predator and prey body sizes in marine food webs. *Ecology*, 89(3), pp.881–881. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1890/07-1551.1> . Data provided by Carolyn Barnes. Also available at <http://www.esapubs.org/Archive/ecol/E089/051/> . <https://github.com/globalbioticinteractions/barnes/archive/8acd34a47c039cedc77e876c4a99a3594db6c2026-06-02T14:09:25.078Z> hash://md5/c971a5e01da53ef0227eee7a8c1d9ce7

Methods

The review is performed through programmatic scripts that leverage tools like Preston (Elliott et al. 2025), Elton (Kuhn, Poelen, and Leinweber 2025), Nomer (Salim and Poelen 2025), globinizer (J. Poelen, Seltmann, and Mietchen 2024) combined with third-party tools like grep, mlr, tail and head.

Table 1: Tools used in this review process

tool name	version
preston	0.11.1
elton	0.16.11
nomer	0.6.5
globinizer	0.4.0
mlr	6.0.0
jq	1.6
yq	4.25.3
pandoc	3.1.6.1
duckdb	1.3.1
mapserver	7.6.4

The review process can be described in the form of the script below ¹.

```
# get versioned copy of the dataset (size approx. 22.6MiB) under review
elton pull globalbioticinteractions/barnes

# generate review notes
elton review globalbioticinteractions/barnes \
> review.tsv

# export indexed interaction records
elton interactions globalbioticinteractions/barnes \
> interactions.tsv

# export names and align them with the Catalogue of Life using Nomer
elton names globalbioticinteractions/barnes \
| nomer append col \
> name-alignment.tsv
```

or visually, in a process diagram.

Figure 1: Review Process Overview

¹Note that you have to first get the data (e.g., via `elton pull globalbioticinteractions/barnes`) before being able to generate reviews (e.g., `elton review globalbioticinteractions/barnes`), extract interaction claims (e.g., `elton interactions globalbioticinteractions/barnes`), or list taxonomic names (e.g., `elton names globalbioticinteractions/barnes`)

You can find a copy of the full review script at [check-data.sh](#). See also [GitHub](#) and [Codeberg](#).

Results

In the following sections, the results of the review are summarized ². Then, links to the detailed review reports are provided.

Files

An extensive list of files produced as part of the review process can be found in [Appendix A. Review Files](#).

Archived Dataset

Note that *data.zip* file in this archive contains the complete, unmodified archived dataset under review.

Biotic Interactions

Figure 2: Biotic Interaction Data Model

In this review, biotic interactions (or biotic associations) are modeled as a primary (aka subject, source) organism interacting with an associate (aka object, target) organism. The dataset under review classified the primary/associate organisms with specific taxa. The primary and associate organisms The kind of interaction is documented as an interaction type.

The dataset under review, named `globalbioticinteractions/barnes`, has fingerprint hash: `://md5/c971a5e01da53ef0227eee7a8c1d9ce7`, is 22.6MiB in size and contains 34,931 interactions with 1 unique type of association (e.g., eats) between 93 primary taxa (e.g., *Thunnus alalunga*) and 191 associated taxa (e.g., fish unidentified).

An exhaustive list of indexed interaction claims can be found in gzipped csv, tsv, geopackage and parquet archives. To facilitate discovery, a preview of claims

²Disclaimer: The results in this review should be considered friendly, yet naive, notes from an unsophisticated robot. Please keep that in mind when considering the review results.

available in the gzipped html page at [indexed-interactions.html.gz](#) are shown below.

The exhaustive list was used to create the following data summaries below.

Table 2: Sample of Indexed Interaction Claims

sourceTaxonName	interactionType	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
Rhizoprionodon terraenovae	eats	teleosts/molluscs/crustaceans	Bethune-D. M., Buckel, J. A. and Carlson, J. K. 2004. Foraging ecology of the early life stages of four sympatric shark species Marine Ecology-Progress Series 268: 245-264.
Rhizoprionodon terraenovae	eats	teleosts/molluscs/crustaceans	Bethune-D. M., Buckel, J. A. and Carlson, J. K. 2004. Foraging ecology of the early life stages of four sympatric shark species Marine Ecology-Progress Series 268: 245-264.
Rhizoprionodon terraenovae	eats	teleosts/molluscs/crustaceans	Bethune-D. M., Buckel, J. A. and Carlson, J. K. 2004. Foraging ecology of the early life stages of four sympatric shark species Marine Ecology-Progress Series 268: 245-264.

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
Rhizoprionodon terraenovae	eats	teleosts/molluscs/crustaceans	Steele, D. M., Buckel, J. A. and Carlson, J. K. 2004. Foraging ecology of the early life stages of four sympatric shark species Marine Ecology-Progress Series 268: 245-264.

Table 3: Most Frequently Mentioned Interaction Types (up to 20 most frequent)

interactionTypeName	count
eats	34931

Table 4: Most Frequently Mentioned Primary Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	count
Thunnus alalunga	3581
Squalus acanthias	3287
Gadus morhua	2518
Thunnus albacares	2113
Thunnus thynnus	1909
Thunnus obesus	1898
Merluccius bilinearis	1389
Dicentrarchus labrax	1315
Mustelus canis	1313
Raja ocellata	1290
Pomatomus saltatrix	1288
Nototheniops larseni	1268
Pleuragramma antarcticum	856
Raja erinacea	838
Xiphias gladius	827
Urophycis tenuis	791
Lepidorhombus whiffiagonis	679

sourceTaxonName	count
Pollachius virens	576
Urophycis chuss	552

Table 5: Most Frequently Mentioned Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

targetTaxonName	count
fish unidentified	11283
unidentified invertebrate	5090
Maurolicus muelleri	2732
fish	1881
Schistomysis spiritus	1315
Ammodytes sp.	1204
crustacean	1080
unidentified squid	912
copepod	611
Oncaea sp.	605
Oithona sp.	396
Clupea harengus	377
Gonatus steenstrupi	376
Meganyctiphanes norvegica	334
Trachurus trachurus	324
silversides, anchovies and ‘other fish prey’	297
Copepod nauplius	291
calanoid egg	288
Scomber scombrus	257

Table 6: Most Frequent Interactions between Primary and Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	count
Thunnus alalunga	eats	Maurolicus muelleri	2732
Squalus acanthias	eats	fish unidentified	2561
Gadus morhua	eats	fish unidentified	1428
Dicentrarchus labrax	eats	Schistomysis spiritus	1315
Thunnus thynnus	eats	Ammodytes sp.	1176
Thunnus obesus	eats	fish	1130
Merluccius bilinearis	eats	fish unidentified	1076
Raja ocellata	eats	fish unidentified	1040
Mustelus canis	eats	unidentified invertebrate	998

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	count
Gadus morhua	eats	unidentified invertebrate	919
Thunnus albacares	eats	crustacean	836
Pomatomus saltatrix	eats	fish unidentified	773
Thunnus albacares	eats	fish	751
Squalus acanthias	eats	unidentified invertebrate	692
Urophycis tenuis	eats	fish unidentified	644
Raja erinacea	eats	unidentified invertebrate	522
Thunnus obesus	eats	unidentified squid	514
Cynoscion regalis	eats	fish unidentified	500
Nototheniops larseni	eats	Oncaea sp.	493

Interaction Networks

The figures below provide a graph view on the dataset under review. The first shows a summary network on the kingdom level, and the second shows how interactions on the family level. It is important to note that both network graphs were first aligned taxonomically using the Catalogue of Life. Please refer to the original (or verbatim) taxonomic names for a more original view on the interaction data.

Figure 3: Interactions on taxonomic kingdom rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life download svg

You can download the indexed dataset under review at indexed-interactions.csv.gz. A tab-separated file can be found at indexed-interactions.tsv.gz

Geospatial Distribution

If geospatial information was extracted from the dataset under review, the map below will show their distribution. These maps were generated using MapServer (McKenna et al. 2025) tools configured via map configuration `indexed-interactions.map` :

```
MAP
  SIZE 1600 800
  EXTENT -180 -90 180 90
  PROJECTION
```


Figure 4: Interactions on the taxonomic family rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life. download svg

```

"init=epsg:4326"
END
LAYER # MODIS WMS map from NASA
NAME "modis_nasa"
TYPE RASTER
OFFSITE 0 0 0
STATUS ON
CONNECTIONTYPE WMS
CONNECTION "https://gibs.earthdata.nasa.gov/wms/epsg4326/best/wms.cgi?"

METADATA
"wms_srs" "EPSG:4326"
"wms_name" "OSM_Land_Water_Map"
"wms_server_version" "1.1.1"
"wms_format" "image/jpeg"
END
CLASS
STYLE
COLOR 232 232 232
OUTLINECOLOR 32 32 32
END
END

```

```

END
LAYER
  NAME "indexed-interactions"
  TYPE POLYGON
  STATUS ON
  CONNECTIONTYPE OGR
  CONNECTION "indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg"
  DATA "indexed-interactions-h3"
  CLASS
    STYLE
      COLORRANGE 253.0 231.0 37.0 32.0 164.0 134.0
      DATARANGE 1.3424226808222062 4.206421065237989
      RANGEITEM "log_number_of_records"
      OUTLINECOLOR 0 0 0
    END
  END
END
END

```


Figure 5: Hexagonal grid cells indicate that interactions claims are available for selected geospatial area: light yellow means relatively fewer claims, dark green relatively more claims.

Associated data can be found in the geopackage files at `indexed-interactions.gpkg` for point data and `indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg` for data clustered in geospatial h3 hexagonals.

Learn more about the structure of this download at GloBI website, by opening a GitHub issue, or by sending an email.

Another way to discover the dataset under review is by searching for it on the

GloBI website.

Taxonomic Alignment

As part of the review, all names are aligned against various name catalogs (e.g., col, ncbi, discoverlife, gbif, itis, wfo, mdd, tpt, pbdb, and worms). These alignments can help review name usage or aid in selecting of a suitable taxonomic name resource.

Table 7: Sample of Name Alignments

providedName	relationName	resolvedCatalogName	resolvedName
Acanthocepola	HAS_ACCEPTED	col	Acanthocepola
Agonus	HAS_ACCEPTED	col	Agonus
cataphractus			cataphractus
Ammodytes	HAS_ACCEPTED	col	Ammodytes
hexapterus			hexapterus
Ammodytes	HAS_ACCEPTED	col	Ammodytes

Table 8: Distribution of Taxonomic Ranks of Aligned Names by Catalog. Names that were not aligned with a catalog are counted as NAs. So, the total number of unaligned names for a catalog will be listed in their NA row.

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
col	NA	13
col	class	7
col	family	8
col	genus	39
col	gigaclass	1
col	infraorder	1
col	kingdom	2
col	order	8
col	phylum	2
col	species	158
col	suborder	1
col	subphylum	1
col	subspecies	1
col	superorder	2
discoverlife	NA	235
gbif	NA	16
gbif	class	6
gbif	family	8
gbif	genus	41

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
gbif	kingdom	2
gbif	order	9
gbif	phylum	2
gbif	species	158
itis	NA	20
itis	class	6
itis	family	6
itis	genus	30
itis	infraorder	1
itis	kingdom	2
itis	order	10
itis	phylum	2
itis	species	152
itis	subclass	1
itis	suborder	2
itis	subphylum	1
itis	subspecies	1
itis	superclass	1
itis	superorder	1
mdd	NA	234
ncbi	NA	20
ncbi	clade	1
ncbi	class	6
ncbi	family	6
ncbi	genus	31
ncbi	infraorder	1
ncbi	kingdom	1
ncbi	order	9
ncbi	phylum	1
ncbi	species	152
ncbi	subclass	1
ncbi	suborder	2
ncbi	subphylum	1
ncbi	subspecies	1
ncbi	superclass	1
ncbi	superorder	2
pdb	NA	151
pdb	class	8
pdb	family	7
pdb	genus	10
pdb	infraorder	1
pdb	kingdom	1
pdb	order	10
pdb	phylum	2

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
pbdb	species	42
pbdb	subclass	1
pbdb	subkingdom	1
pbdb	superclass	1
pbdb	superorder	1
pbdb	unranked clade	4
tpt	NA	232
tpt	species	2
wfo	NA	230
wfo	genus	4
worms	NA	11
worms	class	6
worms	family	7
worms	genus	33
worms	gigaclass	1
worms	infraorder	1
worms	kingdom	2
worms	order	9
worms	phylum	2
worms	species	158
worms	subclass	1
worms	suborder	2
worms	subphylum	1
worms	superorder	2

Table 9: Name relationship types per catalog. Name relationship type “NONE” means that a name was not recognized by the associated catalog. “SAME_AS” indicates either a “HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME” or “SYNONYM_OF” name relationship type. We recognize that “SYNONYM_OF” encompasses many types of nomenclatural synonymies (ICZN 1999) (e.g., junior synonym, senior synonyms).

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
col	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	249
col	SYNONYM_OF	65
col	NONE	14
discoverlife	NONE	264
gbif	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	291
gbif	SYNONYM_OF	53
gbif	NONE	21
itis	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	228

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
itis	SYNONYM_OF	20
itis	NONE	20
mdd	NONE	262
ncbi	SAME_AS	223
ncbi	SYNONYM_OF	25
ncbi	NONE	21
pdb	NONE	156
pdb	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	124
pdb	SYNONYM_OF	29
tpt	NONE	257
tpt	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	5
wfo	NONE	257
wfo	SYNONYM_OF	2
wfo	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	2
wfo	HAS_UNCHECKED_NAME	1
worms	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	228
worms	SYNONYM_OF	37
worms	NONE	11

Table 10: List of Available Name Alignment Reports

catalog name	alignment results
col	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
ncbi	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
discoverlife	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
gbif	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
itis	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
wfo	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
mdd	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
tpt	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
pdb	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
worms	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)

Additional Reviews

Elton, Nomer, and other tools may have difficulties interpreting existing species interaction datasets. Or, they may misbehave, or otherwise show unexpected behavior. As part of the review process, detailed review notes are kept that document possibly misbehaving, or confused, review bots. An sample of review notes associated with this review can be found below.

Table 11: First few lines in the review notes.

reviewDate	reviewCommentType	reviewComment
2026-06-03T08:23:54Z	summary	https://github.com/globalbioticinteractions/barnes/arc
2026-06-03T08:23:54Z	summary	34931 interaction(s)
2026-06-03T08:23:54Z	summary	0 note(s)
2026-06-03T08:23:54Z	summary	0 info(s)

In addition, you can find the most frequently occurring notes in the table below.

: Most frequently occurring review notes, if any.

For additional information on review notes, please have a look at the first 500 Review Notes in html format or the download full gzipped csv or tsv archives.

GloBI Review Badge

As part of the review, a review badge is generated. This review badge can be included in webpages to indicate the review status of the dataset under review.

Figure 6: Picture of a GloBI Review Badge ³

Note that if the badge is green, no review notes were generated. If the badge is yellow, the review bots may need some help with interpreting the species interaction data.

GloBI Index Badge

If the dataset under review has been registered with GloBI, and has been successfully indexed by GloBI, the GloBI Index Status Badge will turn green. This means that the dataset under review was indexed by GloBI and is available through GloBI services and derived data products.

³Up-to-date status of the GloBI Review Badge can be retrieved from the GloBI Review Depot

⁴Up-to-date status of the GloBI Index Badge can be retrieved from GloBI's API

Figure 7: Picture of a GloBI Index Badge ⁴

If you'd like to keep track of reviews or index status of the dataset under review, please visit GloBI's dataset index ⁵ for badge examples.

Discussion

This review and archive provides a means of creating citable versions of datasets that change frequently. This may be useful for dataset managers, including natural history collection data managers, as a backup archive of a shared Darwin Core archive. It also serves as a means of creating a trackable citation for the dataset in an automated way, while also including some information about the contents of the dataset.

This review aims to provide a perspective on the dataset to aid in understanding of species interaction claims discovered. However, it is important to note that this review does *not* assess the quality of the dataset. Instead, it serves as an indication of the open-ness⁶ and FAIRness (Wilkinson et al. 2016; Trekels et al. 2023) of the dataset: to perform this review, the data was likely openly available, **F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable and **R**eusable. The current Open-FAIR assessment is qualitative, and a more quantitative approach can be implemented with specified measurement units.

This report also showcases the reuse of machine-actionable (meta)data, something highly recommended by the FAIR Data Principles (Wilkinson et al. 2016). Making (meta)data machine-actionable enables more precise processing by computers, enabling even naive review bots like Nomer and Elton to interpret the data effectively. This capability is crucial for not just automating the generation of reports, but also for facilitating seamless data exchanges, promoting interoperability.

Acknowledgements

We thank the many humans that created us and those who created and maintained the data, software and other intellectual resources that were used for producing this review. In addition, we are grateful for the natural resources providing the basis for these human and bot activities. Also, thanks

⁵At time of writing (2026-06-03) the version of the GloBI dataset index was available at <https://globalbioticinteractions.org/datasets>

⁶According to <http://opendefinition.org/>: "Open data is data that can be freely used, re-used and redistributed by anyone - subject only, at most, to the requirement to attribute and sharealike."

to <https://github.com/zygoballus> for helping improve the layout of the review tables.

Author contributions

Nomer was responsible for name alignments. Elton carried out dataset extraction, and generated the review notes. Preston tracked, versioned, and packaged, the dataset under review.

Appendix A. Review Files

The following files are produced in this review:

filename	description
biblio.bib	list of bibliographic reference of this review
check-dataset.sh	data review workflow/process as expressed in a bash script
data.zip	a versioned archive of the data under review
HEAD	the digital signature of the data under review
index.docx	review in MS Word format
index.html	review in HTML format
index.md	review in Pandoc markdown format
index.pdf	review in PDF format
indexed-citations.csv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped comma-separated values file format
indexed-citations.html.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interactions claims in gzipped html file format
indexed-citations.tsv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-interactions-col-family-col-family.svg	network diagram showing the taxon family to taxon family interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)

filename	description
indexed-interactions-col-kingdom-col-kingdom.svg	network diagram showing the taxon kingdom to taxon kingdom interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)
indexed-interactions.csv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions.html.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-interactions.tsv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-interactions.parquet	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format
indexed-interactions.png	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review plotted on a map
indexed-interactions.map	mapserver configuration to plot species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review on a map
indexed-interactions.gpkg	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg	geospatially clustered h3 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-sample.csv	list of species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions-sample.html	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in html format
indexed-interactions-sample.tsv	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in tab-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names.csv.gz	taxonomic names indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-names.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-col.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-col.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-sample.csv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
indexed-names-sample.html	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in html format
indexed-names-sample.tsv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in tab-separated values format

filename	description
interaction.svg	diagram summarizing the data model used to index species interaction claims
nanopub-sample.trig	first 500 species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
nanopub.trig.gz	species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
process.svg	diagram summarizing the data review processing workflow
prov.nq	origin of the dataset under review as expressed in rdf/nquads
review.csv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
review.html.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped html format
review.tsv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
review-sample.csv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
review-sample.html	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in html format
review-sample.tsv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
review.svg	a review badge generated as part of the dataset review process
zenodo.json	metadata of this review expressed in Zenodo record metadata

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